

region ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 550, 390) demonstrate the formation of molecular complex of the substrate with HCl of donor-acceptor type during heating³.

We were, therefore, interested to examine the behaviour of FeCl_3 , SbCl_5 and conc. HCl as spray reagents for detecting carbazole alkaloids. In all cases, the results were found to be similar i.e., the coloured spots were detected (blue, violet, green) on heating the developed chromatograms (either slowly or strongly). The coloured spots could be detected in a minimum concentration of 1 to 4 μg of carbazole or carbazole derivatives.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

A thin layer spread on glass plate of dimension 10 cm \times 20 cm using silica-gel G as the absorbent was prepared. The chromatogram was developed in a solvent system of benzene and chloroform (1 : 1) by usual technique. The carbazole alkaloids examined, were isolated in our laboratory, from the plant sources *Murraya koenigii* Spreng., *Clausena heptaphylla* Wt. and Arn. and *Glycosmis pentaphylla* Retz. D.C. After the development of chromatogram, the spots were detected by spraying first with conc. HCl. On heating the plate at 90°, formation of colour on each of the spots was observed. The coloured spots of different compounds (with R_f) are given in the Table 1. The same experiment was repeated successively using FeCl_3 and SbCl_5 as spray reagent and the results are also shown in the same Table 1. The coloured spots could be detected at a minimum concentration of 1 μg of carbazoles in many cases.

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Synthesis of Some New 1-(Substituted Sulphamidophenyl)-2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(Substituted Benzylidene)-5-Imidazolones

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TIWARI and Satsangi¹ have reported that substituted-5-oxazolinones reacted with primary amines in pyridine to give the corresponding 5-imidazolone. Very recently Srivastava *et al.*² have reported a new series of biologically active analogues of 5-imidazolone by fusing equimolar amounts of substituted-5-oxazolinones and heterocyclic primary amines at 140°.

In the present investigation various 2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolinones(I) obtained by the condensation of acetyl/substituted benzoyl glycine with substituted benzaldehydes, on interaction with various sulphonamides(II) in dry pyridine, furnished 2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone(III). The steps involved in their synthesis are shown in chart I.

Chart I

Comparison of I.R. spectra of III with that of I indicated the absence of characteristic absorption band at 1775 cm^{-1} position assigned for carbonyl absorption of a α -lactone and appearance of bands due to carbon at 1690-1670 cm^{-1} and bands in the vicinity of 1380 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of sulphonamide group. The PMR spectrum (DMSO-d_6) of III₄ (chemical shifts in δ values) showed signals at 7.24-7.58 (*m*, 9H, Ar-H), 7.6-8.5 (*m*, 4H of pyridine ring), 2.25 (*s*, 3H, CH_3), 7.13 (*s*, 1H - CH=) and 9.0 (*s*, 1H, NH).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were routinely checked for their homogeneity

TABLE 1—(SUBSTITUTED SULPHAMIDOPHENYL)-2-METHYL-OR-2-ARYL-4-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE)-5-IMIDAZOLONES(III)

Compd. no.	R	R'	R''	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Found	N %	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	H	Guanidino	155	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ S	18.31		18.28
2.*	CH ₃	H	Dihydrochloro Guanidino	250-52	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ SCl ₂	15.33		15.95
3.	CH ₃	H	Diazino	242-43	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ S	16.70		16.71
4.	CH ₃	H	Pyridino	168	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S	13.41		13.99
5.	CH ₃	H	Phenazolino	160-1	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ S	14.46		14.49
6.	CH ₃	H	Dimidino	142-3	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ S	15.64		15.66
7.	CH ₃	O-H	Guanidino	197-98	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	17.53		17.54
8.*	CH ₃	O-OH	Dihydrochloro Guanidino	242	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄ SCl ₂	14.90		14.89
9.	CH ₃	O-OH	Diazino	142	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	16.08		16.09
10.	CH ₃	O-OH	Pyridino	187-88	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ S	12.93		12.90
11.	CH ₃	O-OH	Phenazolino	202	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ S	14.00		14.02
12.	CH ₃	O-OH	Dimidino	214	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ S	15.13		15.12
13.*	C ₆ H ₅	H	Guanidino	204	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	15.76		15.73
14.*	C ₆ H ₅	H	Dihydrochloro Guanidino	255	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃ SCl ₂	13.50		13.51
15.	C ₆ H ₅	H	Diazino	190	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	14.55		14.55
16.	C ₆ H ₅	H	Pyridino	152	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	11.63		11.66
17.	C ₆ H ₅	H	Phenazolino	128	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ S	12.85		12.84
18.	C ₆ H ₅	H	Dimidino	148	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ S	13.77		13.75
19.	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Guanidino	174-75	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄ S	15.17		15.18
20.	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Dihydrochloro Guanidino	290	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄ SCl ₂	13.12		13.10
21.	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Diazino	192	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄ S	14.11		14.08
22.*	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Pyridino	135-36	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	11.30		11.29
23.	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Phenazolino	159-60	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄ S	12.47		12.47
24.	C ₆ H ₅	O-OH	Dimidino	169	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄ S	13.36		13.33
25.*	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Guanidino	273	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	17.16		17.14
26.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Dihydrochloro Guanidino	300	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₅ O ₃ SCl ₂	14.95		14.93
27.*	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Diazino	291-92	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	15.94		15.97
28.*	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Pyridino	296	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S	13.34		13.33
29.*	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Phenazolino	300	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ S	14.25		14.23
30.*	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	Dimidino	261-62	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃ S	15.15		15.16

Satisfactory C and H analyses were also obtained. Yields for all the compounds were obtained 70 to 85%.

by t.l.c. on silica gel plates and the spots were visualised by exposing them to iodine vapours.

2-Aryl-4-(Substituted benzylidene)-5-oxazolones (Ic-e) :

A suspension of benzoyl glycine or *p*-nitrobenzoyl glycine (0.01 mole) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) was warmed on a sand bath till all the solid dissolved. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into absolute ethanol containing anhyd. NaOAc (3.0 g) and appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mole). The flask was transferred to a waterbath and heated for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from acetone-ethylacetate to give **11c** as orange to yellow crystals ; m.p. 248° ; yield 85% ; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1775 (C=O),

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \\ \parallel \\ \text{C}=\text{C} \end{array}$$

1630 (C=N) 1655 cm⁻¹ (-C=C).

(Found : C, 65.28 ; H, 4.41 ; N, 9.55, C₁₆H₁₀-N₂O₄ requires C, 65.31 ; H, 4.40 ; N, 9.52).

1-(Substituted sulphamidophenyl)-2-Methyl/Aryl-4-(Substituted benzylidene)-5-imidazolone(III) :

A mixture of each of **Ia-e** (0.01 mole) and respective substituted sulphonamide (0.01 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed on a sand bath for 5 hrs under anhydrous conditions. Excess of pyridine was removed by distillation and the concentrated mass was cooled and poured in excess of ice-cold water, the solid thus obtained was thoroughly washed with ice-cold water, filtered and recrystallised from methanol-pet. ether (See Table 1 for details)

Compound **13** gave the following data : $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 1690 (C=O), 1625 (C=N), 1375 cm⁻¹ (-SO₂-NH-).

Found : C, 62.06 ; H, 4.25 ; N, 15.74, C₂₃H₁₉N₅O₃S requires C, 62.02 ; H, 4.26 ; N, 15.73.

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Synthesis of 4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene aniline and Its Reaction with Hydrazine, 2 : 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine, Carboxylic Acid Hydrazides and Ethylmalonate

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PHENYLIMINO group in Schiff's bases could be replaced by phenylhydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine¹, and aromatic benzoic acid hydrazides². It was therefore thought worthwhile to see whether this group is also subject to displacement by hydrazine and ethylmalonate. In this note the reactions of hydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, carboxylic acid hydrazides and ethylmalonate with 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl-benzylidene aniline are described. In each case it has been observed that the phenylimino group in(I) has been replaced by azine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazono, benzoylhydrazono and ethyl-malonate groups to give II, III, IV and V respectively. Direct condensation of 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde³ with hydrazine, 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, hydrazides and malonic-ester also furnished II, III, IV and V respectively. The identities of II, III, IV and V prepared by the above methods were established by means of elemental analysis, m.p., m.m.p. and superimposable i.r. spectra.

I R = -CH = NC₆H₅

(II)

III R = -CH = NNH-C₆H₃(NO₂)₂

IV R = -CH = NNH-CO-C₆H₄(R₁)

(R₁ = H, 2-CH₃, 2-Cl, 3-CH₃, 3-NO₂, 4-NO₂, 4-Cl)

V R = -CH = C(CO₂Et)₂

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary and are uncorrected.

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene-aniline(I) :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzaldehyde (0.01 mol.), aniline (0.01 mol.) and four drops of piperidine were taken in a round bottomed flask and the mixture heated in an oil bath for 5 hours at 100-105°. The product obtained was recrystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p., 97°, (yield, 54%) (Found : C, 81.92 ; H, 6.73 ; N, 11.44%. C₂₄H₂₃N₃ requires C, 81.58 ; H, 6.52 ; N, 11.9%)

N'-N''-Bis-(N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene)-hydrazine(II) :

Method-A :

4-N-Benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.003 mol, 80%), glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and ethanol (4 ml) were refluxed for half an hour. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157°, (yield, 85%). (Found : C, 77.91 ; H, 6.41 ; N, 14.86%. C₃₆H₃₆N₆ requires C, 78.26 ; H, 6.52 ; N, 15.22%).

Method-B :

Schiff's base (0.001 mol), hydrazine hydrate (0.003 mol, 80%), glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and ethanol (4 ml) were refluxed for an hour. The product obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157° (yield, 90.6%).

N'-(2 : 4-Dinitrophenyl)-N''-4-(N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methylbenzylidene)-hydrazine(III) :

Method-A :

To an alcoholic solution of 4-N-benzyl-N-cyanoethylamino-2-methyl benzaldehyde (0.001 mol.), 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol.) was added. The contents were heated for 20 minutes and kept for some time. The dark brown crystals separated were washed with hot ethanol, m.p. 229° (yield, 97.3%). (Found : C, 62.36 ; H, 4.56 ; N, 18.59%. C₂₄H₂₂N₆O₄ requires C, 62.88 ; H, 4.80 ; N, 18.34%).

Method-B :

To an alcoholic solution of the Schiff's base (0.001 mol.), 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.001 mol.) was added. The contents were heated for 20 minutes and kept for some time. The dark brown crystals separated were washed with hot ethanol, m.p. 229°, (yield, 87%).